

adding anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent under vacuum gave the crude product which was purified by crystallisation from benzene to obtain fine crystals of 2-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxy)-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone (4a; 80%), m. p. 124° (Found: C, 63.82; H, 4.95; N, 4.59; S, 10.63. $C_{16}H_{15}NSO_3$, calculated for: C, 63.77; H, 4.98; N, 4.65; S, 10.63%).

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2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxy-5-methylazobenzene as Spectrophotometric Reagent for the Estimation of Nickel(II) and Palladium(II) individually and also from their Binary Mixture

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Manuscript received 22 July 1985, revised 19 May 1986,
accepted 18 June 1986

AZO compounds have already been utilised for spectrophotometric estimation of metal ions^{1,2,6}. Most of the azo compounds utilised for this purpose are 2-hydroxyazobenzene derivatives¹⁻¹². A few reagents which have analogous complexing

capability like the present reagent are 2-carboxy-2'-hydroxy-3',5'-dimethylazobenzene-4-sulphonic acid⁴, 6-carboxy-3'-methyl-6'-hydroxyazobenzene-4-sulphonic acid¹² and 6-carboxy-6'-hydroxy-3',5'-dichloroazobenzene-4-sulphonic acid¹². The present paper introduces a new azo compound, viz. 2-carboxy-2'-hydroxy-5'-methylazobenzene for spectrophotometric determination of Ni^{II} and Pd^{II}. Enhanced sensitivity, fewer interferences and easy separability of Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} can claim its superiority. Moreover, it has been found to produce characteristic coloured complex species in solution with other transitional metal ions like Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ru^{III}, Cr^{III} and Mn^{II} etc., the determinations of which are under investigation. Both Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} form 1:1 complexes with the reagent not only in solution but also in solid state.

Experimental

The reagent 2-carboxy-2'-hydroxy-5'-methylazobenzene was prepared by the method available in literature¹⁵. The reagent solution (1 mg/ml) in absolute ethanol was utilised for experimental investigations. The Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} solutions were made from AnalaR nickel chloride and palladium chloride and standardised by the dimethyl glyoxime method¹⁶. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from the chloride or nitrate salts of sodium, potassium or ammonium. Absorbance measurements were made with a Spectromom-204 spectrophotometer and pH values were determined with a Elico LI-10 pH meter.

Procedure: The ethanolic solution of the reagent (3.0 ml) were added to Ni^{II} solution (3.0 ml), [M]=0.025 mg/ml and ammonium acetate—ammonia buffer solution (5.0 ml) in a final volume of 25 ml made up with ethanol to maintain the optimum pH 7.85 (within the range 6.0 to 10.0). The λ_{max} of the deep red coloured Ni^{II} complex was ascertained at 485 nm against the reagent blank. The λ_{max} of the Pd complex (5.0 ml reagent 1 mg/ml, 3.0 ml Pd, 0.025 mg/ml containing sufficient acid to maintain pH in the range 1.5–3.8) was found to be 560 nm. The colours remained stable for more than 7 days.

Results and Discussion

In the case of Ni^{II} complex, Beer's law was obeyed within 0.50 to 7.0 ppm of Ni^{II}. The molar absorptivity of the complex and the photometric sensitivity according to Sandell¹⁷ were found to be 8300 mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0069 μ g cm⁻², respectively at 485 nm. The corresponding values for Pd^{II} complex were 0.5 to 13.0 ppm, 7109 mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0150 μ g cm⁻², respectively at 560 nm. The 1:1 stoichiometry of the complexes formed were ascertained by Job's method of continuous variation¹⁸ and molar ratio method¹⁹.

Effect of diverse ions: Among the cations, anions and complexing agents tartrate, citrate,

oxalate, UO_2^{II} in case of Pd^{II} and tartrate and thiocyanate in case of Ni^{II} do not interfere in the estimations. Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mg^{II} , Tl^I , Cd^{II} , Rh^{III} , Pt^{IV} and Mo^{VI} do not interfere with the determinations of Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} . Metal ions such as Pd^{II} , V^V , Ti^{IV} , Mn^{II} , Cu^{II} , Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} , Sn^{II} , Ru^{III} , Bi^{III} and Re^{VII} interfere in the estimation of both the metal ions.

Determination of Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} by separation from their binary mixture : To an aliquot of an acidic mixture of both the metal ions taken in a separatory funnel was added 0.1% (w/v) reagent solution (3.0 ml) and the pH of the solution was adjusted to 2.1 by adding requisite amount of 0.1 N HCl in a total volume of 20 ml made up with double-distilled water. The Pd^{II} complex was then quantitatively extracted in CHCl_3 , the extraction being made thrice by adding small portions of chloroform at a time. The absorbances of the solutions after drying over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 were measured at 560 nm against the reagent blank. The aqueous layer remaining after the extraction of Pd^{II} complex was treated with 0.1% (w/v) reagent solution (3.0 ml) and the pH of the solution was adjusted to 7-9 adding ammonium-acetate-ammonia buffer in a final volume of 25 ml. The absorbances of aqueous alcoholic solution of the Ni^{II} complex was then measured at 485 nm against the appropriate reagent blank. Results are stated in Table I.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF Pd^{II} AND Ni^{II} FROM THEIR BINARY MIXTURE

Metal ions ppm	Pd^{II} found ppm	Ni^{II} found ppm
3.00 Pd^{II}	2.98	—
3.00 Ni^{II}	—	3.01
1.00 Pd^{II}	0.99	—
4.00 Ni^{II}	—	4.02
2.00 Pd^{II}	2.02	—
6.00 Ni^{II}	—	5.98

Precision and accuracy : 3 ppm of metal in both the cases in 10 determinations was used for finding standard deviations, the values being $\pm 0.18\%$ for Ni^{II} and $\pm 0.46\%$ for Pd^{II} estimations, respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Professor A. Banerjee and Dr. B. Bhattacharyya, for their help in pursuing the work.

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Trace Determination of Terbium(III), Dysprosium(III) and Erbium(III) using 4-(2-Pyridylazo)resorcinol as an Amperometric Reagent

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Manuscript received 8 March 1985, revised 8 May 1986, accepted 7 June 1986

4-(2-Pyridylazo)resorcinol (abbreviated as PAR) has been widely used for the trace determination¹⁻³ of various transition metal ions. Its use as a spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of rare earths has also been discussed in the literature⁴⁻⁶. The spectrophotometric method can not be used when precipitation occurs, nor it can be applied at the close proximity of the wavelength of absorption of complex and the ligand. PAR has been successfully used as an amperometric reagent for the trace determination of some rare earths^{7,8}, in our laboratory. In continuation to our work, the results of amperometric titration of Tb^{III} , Dy^{III} and Er^{III} with PAR have been reported in this paper. The metal-ligand stoichiometry has been supplemented by spectral analysis.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Solutions of Tb^{III} , Dy^{III} and Er^{III} were prepared by dissolving a calculated quantity of the metal oxide/nitrate of each metal in minimum quantity of hydrochloric acid and making up the solution to